

Research Article

Insoluble Contemporary Problems in the Training of Psychiatrists: Influence of Culture, Society, Economy, Politics, and the Spirit of the Times

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Abstract

This article offers a critical reflection on the main obstacles that hinder the training of good psychiatrists in Brazil, based on 45 years of experience in medical education and clinical practice. It argues that many enter psychiatry seeking to resolve their own internal conflicts, which compromises their listening and empathy. Furthermore, the technician and resolute training, based on biological and fast models, prevents the development of an existential and longitudinal understanding of patients. Psychiatry, in this model, is reduced to pharmacological prescription and referral to professionals from other fields. The article proposes a reevaluation of listening, ethical commitment, the psychiatrist's own moral reform, and the integration between science, humanism, and spirituality as foundations for effective and lasting psychiatry.

Keywords: psychiatry; medical education; clinical ethics; professional formation; spiritual care.

Introduction

Since 1981, I have been involved in teaching medicine and psychiatry, both at undergraduate and postgraduate levels, as well as in medical residency. After more than four decades following the training of physicians and the evolution of psychiatric practice in Brazil, I view with concern a phenomenon that has intensified: the chronic difficulty in forming good psychiatrists. This obstacle is not only technical or scientific it is existential, ethical, and even spiritual.

Psychiatry, unlike other medical specialties, demands more than knowledge and skill: it requires presence, listening, patience, and a long-term commitment to human suffering.

However, what I observe is a massive influx of students and doctors with unresolved emotional difficulties – depression, anxiety, sexual conflicts, existential anguish—who consciously or unconsciously seek to resolve themselves through the choice of psychiatry. This alone already compromises the neutrality and empathy fundamental to the profession.

At the same time, there is a hegemony of a biomedical-mechanical model that aims to “resolve” psychic suffering as if it were an inflamed appendix: with medication, electroconvulsive therapy, magnetic stimulation, ketamine, implantation of brain or vagus nerve electrodes – technological procedures supposedly resolute. Many psychiatrists want to act as obstetricians of the psyche – to resolve quickly, medicate fast, see more patients. This approach, although effective in acute situations, does not transform lives in the medium or long term. Human existence, with its dilemmas, addictions, impulses, and voids, demands something very different: it demands walking alongside the patient.

Upcoming Developments

1. Psychiatry as a Compensatory Choice: The Risks of Dysfunctional Personal Motivation

- Entry into the specialty due to unconscious reasons
- Its effects on listening and the therapeutic bond
- The importance of personal analysis and clinical supervision

2. The Biomedical Model and the Illusion of Technical Resolutivity

- Excessive and early use of medication
- Practice in public services as a distorted training
- The psychiatrist as a “prescriptive appendix”

3. Lack of Preparation for Existential Accompaniment and the Loss of Psychiatry to Other Fields

- Outsourcing of listening to psychologists, therapists, coaches

- Disintegration of psychiatry as a humanistic practice
- The rise of the vague concept of “mental health”

4. The Moral and Spiritual Dimension of Psychiatric Practice

- The psychiatrist as an implicit moral model
- Ethical incoherencies that compromise clinical authority
- The importance of inner reform and spirituality in practice

5. Proposals for a New Training Model

- Integration between science, ethics, and spirituality
- Valuing longitudinal and existential accompaniment
- Training in real environments of human suffering, with time and therapeutic bond

6. Sectoral Conclusion

- The future of psychiatry depends on the courage to return to the essential: listening, commitment, ethics, and presence

Psychiatry as a Compensatory Choice

The Risks of Dysfunctional Personal Motivation

It is common to find, throughout psychiatric training, professionals whose initial motivation to enter the specialty is anchored in personal emotional conflicts. It is not rare to see students and doctors suffering from depression, anxiety, sexual disorders, or even existential crises, seeking psychiatry as an unconscious attempt at self-resolution. This type of choice, far from harmless, has serious ethical and technical implications. The risk here is twofold: on the one hand, such professionals tend to over-identify with certain patients, losing the neutrality necessary for clinical practice; on the other, they avoid or neglect themes that internally confront them, creating blind spots in their practice. Psychiatry demands emotional lucidity incompatible with the refusal of self-knowledge.

Rigorous clinical supervision, personal analysis, and continuous follow-up are indispensable in this training process. Without this, psychiatry risks becoming a narcissistic refuge, and not an ethical practice of listening and care.

The Biomedical Model and the Illusion of Technical Resolutivity

The dominant medical training in Brazil is still strongly influenced by a biomedical, technical model centered on disease and intervention. In psychiatry, this translates into the medicalization of psychic suffering and the search for fast, symptomatic solutions.

Many residents and newly graduated psychiatrists learn to treat patients as collections of symptoms, using scales, protocols, and diagnoses in an automated way.

This approach is reinforced by practical training concentrated in public or emergency services, where time is scarce, patients are poor, and demands are acute. Under these conditions, deep listening is discouraged, and teaching is reduced to prescribing and “clearing beds.” The patient becomes a number, an ICD code, a standardized conduct.

The poor patient—guinea pig of the public health system—is someone who must be “mechanized”; there is no time to listen to him, the line must move. He must be biologized, his problem must be solved quickly, even if no one sees that he returns weekly to the emergency room with anxiety crises, which absurdly burdens the medical-hospital service; or no one sees that he will later become much more expensive or more laborious, occupying an ICU bed (due to suicide, untreated illnesses, medication abuse, accidents, neglect, eating disorders, addictions, etc.).

The result is a psychiatrist who acts more like a brain technician than a doctor of the soul. This superficial psychiatry may have immediate efficacy in acute cases, but it fails miserably in treating chronic, complex, and existential disorders.

There is a clear tendency in medical training to form a “Dr. Spock-type” doctor, Sheldon-type (Big Bang Theory), Monk-type detective, Dr. House, MD – that is, a doctor very focused on mechanical, obsessive, intellectual data, little inclined to social-existential understanding. These doctors will focus heavily on a model: sign-symptom-diagnosis-medication. If they are very intelligent, they will at most focus on “micro-symptoms,” a “micro-semiology,” tending to “medicate micro-symptoms,” resulting in a huge list of medications for the patient.

This is because psychiatric symptoms are multifaceted, countless, multifactorial, very numerous. The doctor must know which symptom is most relevant, which symptom to treat, how to prioritize. For that, he must understand the pathophysiology of the disease, and in psychiatry, pathophysiology implies psychopathology. And psychopathology implies psychological knowledge of the patient, existential interest, knowledge of his life, family, desires, social, economic, professional environment. For pathophysiology, then, the adequate psychiatrist must be interested in existence – and it is here that “charity” meets technique. Without existential interest, the doctor cannot be a good “psychopathologist,” and without psychopathology, he will tend to “medicate symptoms,” “medicate diagnoses,” “medicate micro-semiology,” and this will be a failure.

In some of our articles, on the General Psychiatric Syndrome, we show that psychiatric diagnoses are very inconsistent, and that we need pathophysiology-psychopathology to understand the patient and treat him properly. Many psychiatrists leave their training prepared only to diagnose symptoms and supposed diseases, as if, with that alone, they could treat safely. And this is flawed. But it is a model that is replicated precisely because it does not imply inner reform or genuine interest in the patient's existence.

The mechanization of psychiatry is an “escape” from the real resolution of the problem. The industry of procedures, health plans, pharmaceutical companies, government – all conspire to “mechanize” psychiatry. While the “good office psychiatrists” are those who dedicate themselves most to listening and the existence of their patients. But psychiatrists are not trained – in current socialist, mega-capitalist, meta-capitalist environments – to be individuals, to be autonomous; they are trained to be employees of a system, of an industry.

If they were to be “individuals,” for example, caring for their own office, day hospital, or hospital, they would have to strive on the existential-psychological-comprehensive-human-moral side of psychiatry – including because that is the only way they can overcome mechanical competition and truly survive in the survival jungle, even to earn money.

Lack of Preparation for Existential Accompaniment and the Loss of Psychiatry to Other Fields

Psychiatry, when practiced in depth, requires a lasting bond with the patient. It demands walking alongside them in their most intimate issues: alcoholism, nymphomania, pedophilia, impulse control disorders, narcissism, sexual compulsions, various addictions. Many of these conditions are not resolved merely with medications – they require existential change. However, many current psychiatrists avoid this type of follow-up. Whether due to technical unpreparedness or emotional avoidance, they delegate listening to psychologists, therapists, social workers, or even coaches. Psychiatry becomes peripheral – a pharmacological arm of other fields. In many countries, people no longer speak of psychiatry, but of “mental health” – a generic, diluted term, devoid of a clear medical identity.

This loss of territory is symptomatic: psychiatry is disappearing – a new “medical specialty” of “mental health” is emerging – because psychiatrists gave up listening. They reduced themselves to prescribers, symptom technicians, and left the essential – the human encounter – to others.

The Moral and Spiritual Dimension of Psychiatric Practice

Another crucial, often neglected aspect is the ethical and moral commitment of the psychiatrist himself. Psychiatric practice demands not only technical knowledge but personal integrity. How can a doctor who abandons his own child welcome with empathy a child traumatized by paternal absence? How can someone who abuses alcohol, drugs, pornography, severe paraphilias, or compulsions, without hypocrisy, conduct the treatment of a patient with the same problems?

Psychiatry requires inner reform to deal with the existential aspects that chronify and render mental illnesses refractory. The professional who wishes to care for human existences must, himself, commit to his own transformation. This does not mean moral perfection, but coherence, effort, and real ethical commitment.

My personal journey illustrates this point. For many years, I was a “mechanical” psychiatrist – technical, almost a surgeon of the psyche. Only with time, through decades of practice, did I understand that this transforms the patient very little. What truly changes are moral, familial, existential, and spiritual reforms. What heals are gestures of renunciation, sacrifice, charity, patience – not just pharmacological interventions.

Proposals for a New Psychiatric Training Model

Given all of the above, I propose a radical revision of psychiatric training in Brazil. Some fundamental guidelines:

- Training in bond-based, not just emergency environments: it is necessary to learn from real patients, in longitudinal care, not just in short-term hospitalizations;
- Integration between science, humanism, and spirituality: the psychiatrist should not fear the spiritual, as long as it is anchored in ethics and rationality;
- Continuous clinical supervision and mandatory personal analysis: no psychiatrist should practice without having undergone their own emotional journey;
- Valuing listening and presence as central therapeutic instruments: the therapeutic bond heals more than medication;
- Promotion of moral reform as part of the medical identity: a doctor is not just a technician, but an example.

Conclusion

Psychiatry is in crisis not due to lack of science, but due to lack of depth. It is disappearing as an autonomous field because many of its professionals have abdicated listening, ethics, and existential commitment.

Technical teaching, market pragmatism, institutional protocols, and training in dehumanized services are part of the problem. But the greatest obstacle lies within the psychiatrist himself: his refusal to transform.

Good psychiatry begins with a good psychiatrist – and this can only emerge from a personal process of self-knowledge, inner reform, and openness to the existence of the other. Without that, no technique can address human suffering.

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